

MOTIVATING WORKERS AS A KEY FACTOR FOR COMPETITIVENESS IN REGIONAL LABOUR MARKETS

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Abstract. The competitive environment of organisations and the processes of societal change are driving the need and necessity for organisations to react, change and improve their performance. To achieve the organisation's objectives and the best possible performance, the creation of an appropriate working environment becomes a necessity. This environment must not only create the conditions for employees to work professionally but must also help to bring out the best in them. When discussing motivation, pay is often perceived as the primary driving factor. However, in organizational contexts, employees frequently highlight the significance of social rewards, such as verbal encouragement, a sense of responsibility, recognition, and other similar motivators, which are equally essential. Additionally, it is crucial to acknowledge that employee motivation may fluctuate in response to changing environmental factors. In order to carry out work activities effectively, emphasis is placed on the importance of achieving harmony between people and the environment. It is also important to note that staff do not work in a vacuum, there is a constant process of comparison – people are constantly comparing themselves with others, as well as the contribution they make to the work, the result of their work and the rewards they receive.

Keywords: *motivation, labour market, regional development, J. S. Adams' Equity Theory.*

Introduction

Perceptions of contribution and rewards can vary from person to person and are often subjective, so it is essential for managers to understand which outcomes are most important to staff and to ensure that they are fairly measured or distributed. If these components are balanced in the right way, it can be assumed that the employee may feel a sense of fairness, which is likely to have an impact on their motivation. Conversely, when there is no balance, an imbalance prevails, leaving the employee in a perfect environment to believe that equity does not exist and to choose appropriate patterns of behaviour that may not necessarily be based on positive motivation towards the organisation. This is a problem that is relevant to all organisations, and the application of theories of motivation to the situation can help to assess the situation. J. S. Adams' theory of motivation is one of the most popular process theories in the world and today

provides a solution to the challenges of motivating employees and harnessing their competences.

Literature review. Organisations are constantly looking for ways to work better and more efficiently, and to make the most of one of their most important resources: their staff. According to researchers, one of the most significant, but at the same time most challenging, missions of HRM is to ensure that all organizational actors are continuously encouraged to perform well and efficiently and to achieve the organization's long-term goals (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020). Human resources need to be managed in a professional manner, creating a balance between the needs of employees and the needs and capabilities of the organisation. This balance is the key to the development of a company to run its operations productively. Organisations should actively create a culture of work or company formation so that employees feel encouraged to work harder and perform at a higher level.

In terms of organisational culture, motivation, or at least the attempt to create a motivating environment, can be a means by which managers can establish or adjust professional relationships in the work environment. According to Gražulis et al. (2015), in the current HRM process, neglecting employees' personal needs and motives for work can have negative consequences for the organisation as a whole, and managers who ignore them are likely to struggle to increase the efficiency and quality of their subordinates' work and to achieve the organisation's goals. Every employee in an organisation must have hopes or needs, including the need for approval from the environment, as well as internal factors such as self-esteem, achievement, and external factors such as recognition and attention. "It is important to understand motivation, both within employees and in the operating environment, as this will help improve performance" (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020).

When analysing employee motivation, the most commonly used terms are needs, motives and motivation. Researchers interested in the phenomenon of motivation focus on the needs of people and the patterns of satisfying those needs. "Managers who want to manage others effectively need to have a good understanding of their need priorities, a classification of needs, how needs can best be met at work, and how different forms of motivation affect human needs" (Paliduskaitė, 2007). In a general sense, motivation is what drives people to pursue and act. This is confirmed by Gerasimovičius and Sabaliauskas (2020), who state that "motivation drives and directs a person's behaviour towards a goal and helps the person to make sense of his or her actions, to control and change his or her behaviour. In an attempt to understand a person's path towards behavioural change, it is worth analysing Fig. 1, which shows an elementary motivation process. It can be said that "motivation is an internal state that desires change, either in oneself or in the environment" (Reeve, 2018).

Figure 1. The process of motivating employees (Robbins, 2006)

The most popular and clear concepts summarising motivation that can be found in scientific sources are:

- It is an innate, conscious drive towards a certain satisfaction.
- a drive towards or avoidance of something.
- an inner impulse, impetus, impulse that drives a person to do or behave in one way or another (Jančiauskas, 2011).

Table 1 shows the diversity of the concept of motivation and the different authors' interpretations of the scientific literature. They show some differences in the perception of motivation. In one case, motivation is perceived from the perspective of the employee. In the other case, motivation is used to achieve the objectives of the business entity.

Table 1

Definitions of Motivation in the Literature

Author	Definition of motivation
Bhavikatti (2021)	Motivation is an important factor influencing a person's performance.

Author	Definition of motivation
Žaptorius (2007)	Motivation is a force that affects people's intrinsic and extrinsic qualities and influences their behaviour.
Haber (1998)	Motivation is about individual communication with the employee, listening to their needs and expectations, creating the right working conditions and providing the right kind of leadership.
Blašková, Blaško (2010)	Motivation is a system of principles, rules and measures aimed at contributing to the improvement of the motivational atmosphere in order to enhance the motivation of an individual, a group of individuals or the organisation as a whole.
Marcinkevičiūtė (2005)	Motivation – changing the behaviour and performance of employees in the direction desired by employers.
Gražulis et al. (2015)	Motivation is a component of the managerial function which involves influencing the behaviour of employees in order to achieve the organisation's objectives.
Madhumitha, Dhanabakkiyam (2019)	Motivation is a process that encourages people to act and move in a purposeful way to achieve goals.

Looking at the different definitions of motivation put forward by different authors, they all have some common features. It is important to identify three dominant features that characterise the motivation process (Česynienė, Diskienė & Marčinskas, 2002):

1. That stimulates people's behaviour, i. e. encourages them to behave in one way or another.
2. It is what directs this behaviour, or, in other words, this encouragement is aimed at a specific goal.
3. The way in which this behaviour is sustained.

The process of motivation itself is a complex phenomenon, and in order to study motivation in more detail, it would be useful to familiarise oneself with the most popular theories of motivation, their classification and their attributes.

The main theories of motivation. The main aim of motivation theories is to identify and explain the goals that individuals want to achieve, their needs and alternative behavioural patterns. Various theories of motivation have attempted to classify needs according to certain criteria, such as a person's behaviour at work and the motives behind that behaviour. Jančauskas (2011) argues that motivation theories in the scientific literature are usually divided into two strands – needs and process. According to Dubauskas (2006), process theories examine motivation from a different perspective than need motivation theories. They analyse how a person allocates his or her efforts to achieve various goals and how he or she chooses a particular way of behaving. Process theories do not deny the existence of needs but argue that human behaviour is not only determined by needs. Motivation is the desire to do something and is determined by the ability of an action to satisfy a need. In our terminology, a need refers to a physiological or psychological deficit that makes a particular outcome seem attractive" (Robbins, 2006). A fundamental difference that can be observed between the two types of motivation is that in process theories it is important that the person feels motivated all the time, rather than just having a goal to achieve, which is typical of need motivation theories (Table 2).

Table 2

Main differences between needs and process theories

THEORY OF NEEDS	THEORY OF PROCESS
WHAT gives a person the impulse to act in a certain way?	HOW is human behaviour stimulated?
The structure of needs.	The realisation of needs and motives.
The content of motives and motivation.	Transformation of needs into behaviour.
Helping managers to understand the main motives that drive employees.	Helps managers to understand employee behaviour to meet individual needs.

THEORY OF NEEDS	THEORY OF PROCESS
KEY MOTIVATION THEORIES	
Maslow's hierarchy of needs. F. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. D. McClelland's Three Needs Theory.	J. S. Adams' Equity Theory. V. Vroom's Expectation Theory. E. Lawler and L. Porter's Five Variable Motivational Model.

Jančauskas (2011) points out that "in order to apply needs theory in managerial practice, managers need to take into account the diversity of needs, depending on the problems the employee faces in work and life situations". It should also be taken into account that it is necessary to know the personal characteristics, goals and motives of employees and to try to understand why individuals prefer different motives" – if these conditions are met, process-oriented theories of motivation would work well in an organisation. The author of the Hierarchy of Needs argued that needs form a hierarchy. He also argued that as long as primary needs are not satisfied, the satisfaction of higher level needs does not motivate human action (Maslow, 1954).

Process theories explain how people behave to meet individual needs and the effectiveness of a decision. Unlike content theories, process theories of motivation seek to explain how the motivation process works, how it develops and how it leads to specific behaviours. Among the most commonly used theories of process motivation in practice are Vroom's Expectancy Theory, J. S. Adams' Equity Theory, and E. Lawler and L. Porter's Five Variable Motivational Model" (Zakarevičius, 2011). In his analysis of process theories, Dubauskas (2006) identifies, in his opinion, two of the most well-known and popular theories: J. S. Adams' Equity and Vroom's Expectancy, but he also mentions the motivational model of E. Lawler and L. Porter, which is distinguished by its complexity and incorporates components of the aforementioned Equity and Expectancy theories. Vroom's Expectancy Theory shows that the key message of this theory is that motivating employees is invariably linked to the satisfaction of specific expectations. It is a theory of motivation that states that individuals, when deciding which behavioural alternative to choose, choose the one that they believe will lead to the desired outcome (Leonienė, 2008). Vroom's Expectancy Theory argues that not only are the active needs that arise important to an employee's motivation, but also that he or she must expect that the type of behaviour he or she chooses will actually satisfy the needs. This expectancy theory states that there are three variables that influence employee motivation (Sakalas & Šilingienė, 2000):

1. Valence is the value that an individual places on a salary. Valence depends on the value system of each individual. It is the expected importance of the reward to the individual.
2. Instrumentality is the relationship between the amount of achievement and the expected reward (recognition, bonus, intrinsic pride, etc.). Instrumentality is also expressed in terms of the probability that the behaviour will lead to such a reward.
3. Expectations are the link between the employee's perceived effort and achievement. It is expressed as a probability (e. g. can I do it?) and is based on an opinion about one's abilities and chances of success in a given situation.

The main ideas of Vroom's Expectancy Theory:

1. Reward expectations are much more important than we tend to give them credit for. People make decisions and act by focusing more on future events than on past outcomes (consequences).
2. Rewards need to be linked to activities that benefit the organisation.
3. Rewarding organisational performance must take into account the expectations of each employee.
4. Rewards must reflect the employee's effort in performing the task.

It is very important to note that a deeper look at the theory of expectations shows that these three components would probably not be of any benefit in isolation. This means that if any one factor (expectation, instrumentality or valence) is not fulfilled, the desired result would not be achieved. An employee who puts in the effort and achieves good results but has no hope of being recognised may be completely demotivated (Palidauskaitė, 2007). Obviously, every employee evaluates the outcome and the rewards

before taking any action. Therefore, it can be argued that the individual's subjective vision and the manager's ability to properly understand the employees can be exploited for the good of the organisation. Notably, that each employee brings his or her own set of expectations to the workplace, and it is therefore the employer's responsibility to accept, understand and meet these expectations, as this is an important prerequisite for an employee's motivation, engagement and loyalty to the organisation.

A closer look at the theories of process motivation reveals that they are often more in line with today's motivation than theories of needs, which is why the following is a closer look at J.S. Adams' Equity Theory of employee motivation, which is considered to be one of the most prominent and most applicable of the process theories.

J. S. Adams' Equity Theory. J. S. Adams' Equity Theory reasoning is one of the process theories. The first person to address the issue of fairness in the context of motivation in the broadest sense was the world-renowned psychologist J. Stacey Adams (born in 1925), who studied the characteristics of human behaviour in the workplace. The goals of Equity Theory (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2022):

1. Explain how people evaluate the degree of fairness in interpersonal relationships.
2. Explain the impact of unequal relationships.

This theory is based on the idea that "people in an organisation want to be judged fairly and impartially". Adams' theory explains how people perceive and react to fairness and equity in social and professional relationships. Thus, this theory has become one of the most popular theories of motivation in the world up to the present day and is always cited as one of the main procedural theories of motivation. The theory was originally published in 1965 in the scientific journal *Advances in experimental social psychology*, edited by L. Berkowitz (Adams, 1965). According to Adams' Equity Theory, individuals are motivated by a sense of fairness and equity in their relations with others. The theory explicitly states that unfair rewards for work affect the quality of work and attitudes towards work. Fairness in this theory can be defined as the relationship between an employee's resources and the rewards received for work. At the point at which two people exchange something, there is a likelihood that one or both of them will feel that the exchange was unfair (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2022). As Adams argues, this is often the case when a person exchanges his or her services for a salary (Adams, 1965). The scientist identifies three cases of equity balance or imbalance:

1. Equity occurs when the input-to-reward ratio of one employee is perceived to be equivalent to that of another employee.
2. Negative inequity – when the ratio of reward to labour input is less than that of the other.
3. Positive inequity – when the ratio of reward to labour input is greater than that of the other.

Inequity occurs not only when a person receives too little benefit, but also when he or she receives too much benefit (Davlembayeva & Alamanos, 2022). As J. S. Adams himself wrote, if the rewards received are proportional to the effort put in by the employee, then the employee feels satisfied and motivated (Adams & Freedman, 1976). On the other hand, a person feels inequity when his efforts are not compensated by the rewards received (Targamadze, 1996). Fig. 2 shows that inequity creates many negative consequences, but their elimination creates conditions for new and meaningful activities. This can enrich not only the company, but also the worker, who has found meaning in his or her activity.

Figure 2. Inequity as a motivational process (Jucevičienė, 1996)

J. S. Adams' Equity Theory develops four important propositions regarding unfair rewards (Robbins, 2006):

1. If paid for the time they work, over-rewarded workers will do more than fairly rewarded ones.

2. If paid for the quantity of output, overpaid workers will produce fewer, but better-quality units than fairly paid workers.
3. If rewarded for time worked, underpaid workers will produce less or lower quality work.
4. If rewarded for the quantity of output, underpaid workers will produce large quantities of low-quality units compared to fairly paid workers.

If a worker feels unfairness, he or she may choose one of the following:

1. The worker can distort either his or her own or others' inputs and rewards.
2. The employee can change his/her own contributions and rewards by behaving differently. For example, applying self-righteousness by working less and trying less at work.
3. Choose another worker to compare.
4. As a last resort, you may choose to quit your job (Robbins, 2006).

Fairness at work and pay are significantly related. Reward policy depends directly on fairness as it reveals the employer's intentions towards the employee. Fig. 3 shows that adequate remuneration can, at least in the short term, lead to higher productivity. However, adequate motivation to work is more closely linked to productivity growth, and the design and development of motivation systems would generate more benefits for both the company and the employee.

Figure 3: The link between equity and reward (Al-Zawahreh, Al-Madi, 2012)

As Miner states, Equity Theory is considered one of the most valid frameworks for understanding human attitudes and motivation' (Miner, 1984). It is also supported by a large body of research and provides important motivational suggestions. The use of motivational tools such as recognition, career opportunities, freedom to make decisions and others that can stimulate intrinsic motivation is only effective when it is applied to each employee individually according to his or her needs (Šalkauskienė & Šakūnaitė, 2022).

Based on J. S. Adams' Equity Theory, it can be concluded that it is the sense of fairness and equity that motivates individuals in their relationships with others. It is the sense of fairness that enables a person to feel motivated all the time. Adams' theory of motivation can be described as a constant balancing act between the contributions that employees make to their work and the results that they receive. Finding this right balance helps to achieve a strong and productive relationship with the employee – which is the goal of every organisation – in which case the overall result is satisfied, motivated employees.

Conclusions

Motivation is an important phenomenon in modern organisations. Motivation is divided into two strands according to models of human behaviour: needs and process. The essential difference between these two types of motivation is that in process theories, it is important that the person feels motivated all the time, not just that he or she has a goal to achieve, which is the case in need-based motivation theories. It is very important to use a variety of motivational tools in an organisation. A combination of measures that affect both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of the individual is ideal. These measures have the greatest impact when they consider the individual employee and his or her needs.

One of the most applicable theories, based on a large body of research in the process area, is J. S. Adams' theory of motivation. It explains how people perceive and react to fairness and equity itself in social and professional relationships. The theory explicitly states that unfair rewards for work have a significant impact on the quality of work and on attitudes towards work itself. Adams' Equity Theory can be described as a constant balancing act between the worker's contribution to the job and the results they receive. An individual's internal objections to unfairness can be a motivating reason for striving for that balance. Finding and maintaining this right balance helps to achieve a strong and productive relationship with the employee – which is the goal of every organisation.

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